

A study on Etiological and Microbiological Profile of Suppurative Keratitis in North Karnataka PopulationVikas Shankarrao¹, Pranesh Kulkarni², Abhishek Kulkarni³¹Post Graduate Student, Department of Ophthalmology, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Khaja Banda Nawaz University, Kalaburagi, Karnataka-585102²Professor and Head, Department of Ophthalmology, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Khaja Banda Nawaz University, Kalaburagi, Karnataka-585102³Associate Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Faculty of Medical Sciences, Khaja Banda Nawaz University, Kalaburagi, Karnataka-585102

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Abstract:**Background:** The main cause of blindness in the world today is corneal disease, which remains second only to cataracts because it includes a wide variety of infections and inflammatory eye diseases. To evaluate the epidemiological trends and risk factors associated with suppurative corneal ulceration and to identify the microbial agents responsible for these corneal infections.**Method:** 100 patients aged between 10 to 75 years with suppurative keratitis were studied. Corneal ulcers were clinically diagnosed with the help of slit-lamp fundus examination. Visual acuity measured with the help of Snellen's chart, Routine blood examination, HIV, Hbs-Ag were done. Corneal scraping done with a No. 15 Bard-Parker blade & subjected for Microbiological evaluation. Microbiological investigation includes gram staining, 10% KOH preparation, and bacterial culture using blood agar and chocolate agar. Fungal culture was done on Sabouraud's dextrose agar medium.**Results:** 95% people with corneal ulcer had trauma by vegetative matter and foreign body as predisposing factor for keratitis and late presentation of patient to Ophthal OPD, as patient got treated at local hospital by corticosteroid for foreign body (5%). The maximum duration of symptom was 81% in 1-10 days; >20 days was 1% in patients. Gram stain reported 91.8% sensitivity for bacteria, fungi 89.8% sensitivity, 10% KOH had 61% positive, 39% negative patients. Fusarium, Aspergillus Spp being most common fungal & Staphylococcus Aureus being most common pathogens corneal ulcer.**Conclusion:** The present pragmatic, different microbiological profile study will certainly help the ophthalmologist treat such patients efficiently to prevent blindness.**Keywords:** Slit lamp, Snellen's chart, Fluorescein staining, No.15 Bard parker Blade, 10% KOH..This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Bacterial and fungal keratitis are infections of the cornea that is characterized by inflammation, often with stromal infiltration by leukocytes, and is considered an ophthalmic emergency requiring immediate attention. Both infections and immune mechanisms are important in the development of this sight threatening condition [1].

Keratitis can progress rapidly with corneal destruction through pathological wound healing within 24-48 hours. It leads to permanent visual dysfunction, reported globally [2]. Initial management of microbial keratitis is empiric with broad-spectrum topical antimicrobials, as with current microbiological investigations, it can take days or even weeks to identify a causative organism. Furthermore, topical therapy has limitations, including high tear turno-

ver, and ocular toxicity [3]. Patients with suppurative keratitis continue to lose vision and suffer ocular pain and discomfort [4].

Hence, improved therapies for keratitis are required, while more rapid and correct identification of the infection agents supports a more effective treatment. Therefore, an attempt is made to evaluate the etiological and microbiological profile of suppurative keratitis.

Material and Methods

Study included 100 (one hundred) patients aged between 10 – 75 years, attending ophthalmology OPD at Khaja Banda Nawaz Teaching and General Hospital Kalaburgi, Karnataka. The samples were collected from August 2022 to February 2024.

Inclusive Criteria: Clinically diagnosed patients of corneal ulcer (before initiating antimicrobial therapy or discontinuing for 12-48 hours) and selected patients who gave their consent in writing for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Non-compliant patients, patients with viral ulcers, healing ulcers, Mooren's and marginal ulcers, neurotrophic ulcers, and ulcers associated with auto-immune disorders.

Method: History was taken elaborately in every patient. The examination of corneal ulcer anterior segment and posterior segment was carried out with the help of a slit lamp bio microscope. Visual acuity was noted with the help of Snellen's chart, Fluorescein staining was carried out. Blood examination included a complete hemogram, random blood sugar, HIV, HbsAg.

Corneal scraping was carried out by an ophthalmologist under strict aseptic conditions using a sterile Bard-Parker blade (No. 15). Before the procedure, preservative-free 4% lignocaine hydrochloride was applied. Samples were collected from the leading edge and base of each ulcer. These samples were then inoculated onto blood agar, chocolate agar, nutrient agar, and Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) and spread on two slides — one for Gram staining and the other for 10% KOH wet mount preparation [Fig.3].

Standard protocols were followed for all laboratory procedures. The inoculated blood agar and chocolate agar plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. If no growth was observed, incubation was extended for another 24 hours. The criteria for a positive microbial diagnosis included:

- The same organism growing on two or more culture media.
- Growth of the same organism from repeated scrapings.
- Compatibility of the findings with clinical symptoms.
- Smear results aligning with culture findings.

Bacterial colonies were identified based on Gram stain microscopy and biochemical characteristics using standard laboratory methods. SDA plates were incubated at 27°C and monitored daily for up to three weeks for fungal growth. Fungi were identified based on their colony morphology on SDA and the microscopic appearance of hyphae and spores using lactophenol cotton blue staining.

Statistical analysis:

Various parameters of etiology and microbiology are classified by percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out in SPSS software. The ratio of males and females was 2:1.

Figure 1: Bacterial Keratitis

Figure 2: Fungal Keratitis

Figure 3: 10% KOH mount of the scrapping material showing fungal hyphae

Observation and Results

Objective and Results

Table 1: History of trauma (Mode of insult) wise distribution of keratitis – 39 (39%) FB, 39 (39%) Trauma, 17 (17%) quack, 5 (5%) cortico-steroid

Table 2: Sensitivity and specificity of corneal scraping in detection of Bacteria –

- Gram’s Stain: 91.8 sensitivity, 98.9% Specificity,

- Fungi: A gram stain sensitivity 89.9%, Specificity 93.7%

- 10% KOH: 90.6% sensitivity, 95.3% Specificity

Table 3: Duration of symptoms wise distribution of keratitis patients – 81%: 1-10 days 18%, 11-20 days 1%, >20 days mean SD 8.11 (±6.3)

Table 4:

10% KOH and surgical treatment wise distribution of patients – 10% KOH: 61% positive, 39% negative, surgical treatment 14% yes and 86% NO

Table 5: Gram stain wise distribution of patients – 36% Gram positive bacteria 1%, gram negative 23% hybrid, 40% No bacteria seen

Table 6: Distribution of patients on treatment wise – 46% MS, 35% MT, 11% M. TPK, 3% MTAB. CLT, 2% MTS, 1% MTABCL, TPK 1%, M. TABCLS, 1% MOPK

Table 1: History of trauma (Mode of insult) wise distribution of keratitis patients

History of trauma	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
Foreign Body	39	39.0
Trauma	39	39.0
Quack	17	17.0
Co-St	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Figure 4: History of trauma (Mode of insult) wise distribution of keratitis patients

Table 2: Sensitivity and specificity of corneal scraping in detection of Bacteria and fungi

Bacteria	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Gram's stain	91.8	98.9
Fungi	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Gram's stain	89.8	93.7
10% KOH	90.6	95.3

Figure 5: Sensitivity and specificity of corneal scraping in detection of Bacteria and fungi

Table 3: Duration of symptoms wise distribution of keratitis patients

Duration of symptoms in days	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
1 – 10	81	81.0
11 – 20	18	18.0
>20	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0
Mean ±SD	8.11 days ± 6.34	

Figure 6: Duration of symptoms wise distribution of keratitis patients

Table 4: 10% KOH and surgical treatment wise distribution of patients

Variables		Number of patients	Percentage (%)
10% KOH	Positive	61	61.0
	Negative	39	39.0
Surgical Treatment	Yes	14	14.0
	No	86	86.0

Figure 7: 10% KOH and surgical treatment wise distribution of patients

Table 5: Gram stain wise distribution of patients

Gram stain	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
Gram Positive Bacteria	36	36.0
Gram Negative Bacteria	1	1.0
Hybrid	23	23.0
No Bacteria seen	40	40.0
Total	100	100.0

Figure 8: Gram stain wise distribution of patients

Table 6: Treatment combination wise distribution of patients

Treatment combination	Number of patients	Percentage (%)
M,S	46	46.0
M,T	35	35.0
M, TPK	11	11.0
M,TABCL,T	3	3.0
M, T, S	2	2.0
M,TABCL,TPK	1	1.0
M, TABCL,S	1	1.0
M,OPK	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

M = Medical S=Surgery T=Topical, OPK = Optical peretratingkeratoplasty, TPK = Therapeutic Penetrating keratoplasty, TABCL = Tissue adhesive and bandage contact lenses

Figure 9: Treatment combination wise distribution of patients

Discussion

Present study carried out to evaluate the etiological and microbiological profile of suppurative keratitis in the North Karnataka population. Cause for the keratitis were 39% Trauma, 39% had a foreign body and the same number of traumas. 17% by quacks, 5% by corticosteroids were observed (Table 1). In the study of sensitivity and specificity of corneal scraping for detection of bacteria, there was 91.8% sensitivity, 98.9% specificity of bacteria, 89.9% sensitivity, and 93.7% specificity of fungal infection. In 10% KOH, 90.6% sensitivity and 95.3% specificity were studied to distinguish yeast and filamentous fungi (Table 2). The duration of symptoms of 81% of patients was 1–10 days, >20 days had only 1 patient; mean value: 8.11 (\pm 6.3) (Table 3). In the study of KOH in the microbiological study, 61% were positive, and surgical treatment was 14% (Table 4). In the study of gram stain, 36% were positive, and 23% were hybrid (Table 5). In combination treatment, MS (medical and surgical) therapy was highest 46% and 35% was MT (medical and topical) (Table 6) (Figure 1, 2, and 3). This study is more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Bacterial keratitis is a serious ocular infectious disease that can lead to severe visual disability. The severity of corneal infection visually depends on the underlying conditions of the cornea and the pathogenicity of the infection bacteria. Many patients have poor clinical outcomes. [8] Fungal keratitis, due to filamentary fungi, is typified by a gray-white infiltrate with irregular feathery margins and raised borders, along with suppuration, hypopyon, and satellite lesions. Descemet's fold and immune ring with minimal surrounding infiltrate Filamentous fungi. *Fusarium* SPP and *Aspergillus* SPP found to be common in mycotic keratitis. However, in some cases etiologies exhibited by unicellular fungi, such as yeasts of the *Saccharomycetaceae* and *Tremellaceae* families, are often clinically similar to those of bacterial keratitis. The majority of identified organisms are true fungi, or mycota [9]. A range of treatments include Natamycin, azoles such as fluconazoles and voriconazoles. [10]. Similar to fungal keratitis, the severity of bacterial infections is largely dependent on the causative agent's staphylococcus epidermidis, streptococcus pneumoniae, and pseudomonas aeruginosa, which are common pathogens associated with bacterial keratitis [11]. The primary treatment for bacterial keratitis is the immunotherapeutic use of fluoroquinolones in treating bacterial keratitis. It is important to note that in treating keratitis, clinical or pathological findings are mandatory [12]. The resistance to ocular infections may be overestimated.

Summary and Conclusion

In the present study, Gram stain showed bacterial isolates in 39% of total cases, and KOH 10% mounts were in agreement with 61% of cases, so it can be used as a quick and reliable method to find out the fungal etiology of corneal ulcers, and treatment can be started immediately without waiting for the culture reports to arrive. Surgical debridement of the ulcer in the initial stages helped reduce the microbiological load and drug penetration. However, caution was exercised in ulceration with thin floors. Penetrating keratoplasty was done in non-healing ulcers and perforated ulcers, with 2-4 weeks of follow-up. The present study demands that such clinical trials be conducted on a large number of patients in hi-tech research center of ophthalmology to combat any type of side effects or overdosage of drugs because there is a lack of information concerning the pathogenesis of how the different types of microbial keratitis develop and the host factors involved.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location of research centre, small number of patients lack of latest techniques we have limited finding and results.

This research work has been approved by the ethical committee of Faculty of Medical Sciences, Khaja Banda Nawaz University, Kalaburagi, and Karnataka-585102.

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